

FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE SUSTAINABILITY OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT IN MODERN SOCIETY

Kurbanov Ikhtiyor Khikmatovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute
named after Abu Ali Ibn Sino,
department of "Pedagogy. Psychology and Languages"
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6283733>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2022
Accepted: 15th February 2022
Online: 20th February 2022

KEY WORDS

globalization, humanization,
innovative personality,
innovation, intellectual
initiative, information
technology, communological
orientation, innovation
motivation, synergetic style of
thinking, sociocentrism.

ABSTRACT

The impact of a person's innovative potential, which is a complex of personal qualities that ensures a person's psychological readiness to create new forms of activity for the development and dissemination of innovative educational products, as well as self-development and personal growth of information, is discussed in this article. Certain specific variables that contribute to the development of a creative personality are recognized, as well as the political implications of this phenomenon.

Introduction

Today, innovation is the foundation of any country's long-term development. From the invention of the earliest tools to the discovery of algorithms and nanoparticles, modern creative computers, and other high technologies, history has proved that man has come a long way with his intelligence. At the same time, this has a negative impact on not just the educational system, but also the overall development of society. As a result, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan named 2018 the Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Support for Innovative Ideas and Technologies in order to counteract this effect and disruption. "Today, we are embarking on a path of inventive development aiming at a dramatic

regeneration of the state's and society's life. Of course, this isn't a coincidence. Because, in today's fast-paced world, who will win? The state that relies on new ideas and innovation wins. Innovation is the way of the future. We must start with fresh ideas and techniques if we are to build a wonderful future today." [1]

Main part

Based on market demand, an innovation is one that is provided to assure a qualitative gain in the efficiency of processes and products. The end product of the creative process, discoveries, inventions, and rationalizations is man's intellectual activity, his imagination. The term "innovation" comes from the Latin word "novatio," which means "upgrade" (or

"change"), and the suffix "in" is translated from Latin as "in the direction," he stated. The concept of innovation first arose in nineteenth-century scientific study.

"Walking down the route of constructing a contemporary state based on a developed market economy and assuring a steady transition from a strong state to a strong civil society, we just need modern knowledge," said the first President I.A. Karimov. We've always believed that the strategic development targets we've set for ourselves can only be achieved by people with potential and advanced technologies." [2] The Austrian and American economist J. Schumpeter analyzed "creative combinations," changes in the development of economic systems, at the turn of the twentieth century, using the idea of "innovation." In the early 1900s, Schumpeter was one of the first economists to coin the word.

Despite widespread misconceptions, innovation is different from invention. The difference between innovations and scientific discoveries and inventions is the following:

- Science is the transformation of certain resources into knowledge and ideas;
- Innovation is the transformation of knowledge and ideas into funds;
- An invention is the creation of a new concept;
- Innovation is emphasizing the practical significance of an invention and turning it into a successful market product;

Thus, we should look at innovations not as innovations of any kind, but as a

factor that significantly increases the efficiency of thinking in a developing society.

In the view of the foregoing, "pure" science may partially contradict human nature, because it is based on schematic simplifications and models, in some cases impoverishing the completeness of the picture of the surrounding world. By violating the unity of natural interconnections, the "classical" scientist himself can unwittingly complicate the prospect of turning his scientific developments into innovations. The central link in the philosophy of innovation is the concept of individuality, understood as authenticity, associated with non-conventionality (non-agreement) and "non-scientific", as well as openness and sensitivity to other points of view. The main provisions of the philosophy and psychology of innovation are addressed to the individual experience of the subject, the freedom of various interpretations and respect for the uniqueness of each person.[3]

The psychological preparedness to generate new forms of activity for the development and dissemination of innovative educational products, as well as self-development and personal growth as a strategic factor in efficient professional activity, is the creative potential of an individual. The objective, motivational, creative, prognostic, transformational functions, the function of development and formation of novel professionally oriented experience are all implemented by the individual's inventive resource in the university's scientific and educational

environment. The following components make up an individual's inventive potential:

- innovative orientation, integrating a set of motives and values that determine the innovative, acmeological nature, the desire to achieve the heights of professional excellence, enrichment of innovative experience, awareness of the importance of innovative processes in educational practice, reflecting the psychological attitude towards the development of the personality of students and their own self-development as personally necessary; - innovative competence, reflecting the systemic level of formation of innovative knowledge, skills and experience of innovative activity, the ability to create, create a new product, introduce new technologies and methods into the educational process, acting as a measure of readiness to use one's innovative potential to achieve the innovative goals of professional activity as efficiently as possible ; - innovative creativity as the ability for creativity, innovation and forecasting, aimed at achieving a specific practical goal, involving the generation of new, potentially useful ideas and obtaining a result ready for use in further practice. The problem of forming the psychological readiness of specialists for innovative activity in the leading areas of the development of society determines the need for psychological research on various aspects of innovative activity and the preparation of competitive professionals for it.[4] The social order of society for the effective implementation of social policy focuses on the formation of specialists who are ready and able to innovate, show creativity, actively transform and master

advanced domestic and foreign experience, knowledge, modern professional values, models and technologies, as well as all the qualities that would allow the future specialist in the social sphere to effectively carry out innovative activities in social institutions. The essence and value of such psychological readiness for innovative activities of social specialists is manifested in their willingness and ability to focus on an effective creative approach in solving all social problems, performing professional activities based on attracting the potential of new models, algorithms and technologies to solve social problems of a person and society. [5] On the other hand, despite the presence of such an acute scientific and practical problem, the formation of psychological readiness for innovative activity of social sphere specialists has not been studied enough by psychological science: a systematic approach has not been developed, scientifically based decisions on topical areas of formation of psychological readiness of social sphere specialists for innovative activities. The main priority for the modernization of all aspects of the functioning of society in modern conditions is the social sphere. The activation of innovative activity in social work will be able to perform a social and innovative function in society to improve the mechanisms for solving social problems.

The main aspects of the formation of innovative competencies among future specialists in the social sphere, which orient them to innovative activity in the context of dynamic socio-economic changes, are laid out in the state educational standards of the third generation, among which, first and foremost, it is necessary to indicate the

readiness to generate and implement innovative ideas and technologies in the social sphere. The solution of this problem requires the creation of optimal conditions for the formation of key characteristics of psychological readiness for innovative activity, the quality of which is determined by the development of students' motivational focus on this activity, the formation of professionally significant qualities in them, satisfaction with those aspects of educational activity that are more significant in the development of a professional, the formation cognitive, operational, emotional-volitional and communicative components of readiness for innovative activity.[6] Thus, in connection with the constantly changing socio-cultural and socio-economic conditions for the development of our country and modernization processes at all levels of education, the needs of pedagogical theory and practice are also changing, among which is the search for ways to improve the process of vocational training, training and retraining of specialists in the field of social work in a higher education institution.

Conclusion

Therefore, as the socio-cultural and socio-economic conditions for our country's

development and modernization processes at all levels of education change, so do the needs of pedagogical theory and practice, one of which is the search for ways to improve the process of vocational training, training, and retraining of social work specialists in a higher education institution. An analysis of the socio-economic situation and the needs of the labor market for professionals in various areas of the social sphere show the urgent need to form a specialist in the social sphere of a new formation: a researcher, scientist, inventor, designer, supporter of the development and implementation of new social technologies.[7] In addition, one should take into account the fact that modern processes in society, changes in socio-cultural priorities make it necessary to update the areas of society, one of which is the social sphere. Innovations in the social sphere are a natural and necessary condition for its development in accordance with the constantly changing needs of society. Under these conditions, one of the priority tasks of modern higher education is to intensify the development of new technologies aimed at ensuring the process of forming the readiness of social specialists to work in changing conditions - the lack of social technologies and innovative social programs.

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